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GERMINATED ALFALFA SEED IN WHEAT BREAD FORMULATIONS: TRACKING THE PROTEIN STRUCTURAL CHANGES BY MEANS OF ATR-FTIR SPECTROSCOPY

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An insight into the chemical composition and molecular structure of heterogeneous food components undergoing structural and conformational changes during product development can provide useful guidelines toward components assembly in creating acceptable new product. This becomes particularly important in products such as bread in which gluten network plays a key role in defining the product structure and where other ingredient involvement tends to impair the gluten network and reflect on the bread's technological quality and acceptance by consumers. The objective of this study was to identify the major components and detect the conformational changes in protein secondary structures in wheat bread induced by the addition of germinated (GASF) and non-germinated (ASF) alfalfa seeds flour (5 and 10%) using Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy with attenuated total reflectance as sampling technique (ATR-FTIR). The ATR-FTIR spectra confirmed the presence of major components in alfalfa flours and resulting breads including protein, starch, and lipids. Further deconvolution of the Amide I protein region revealed the presence of β -sheets, α -helix and β -turn protein secondary structures in flour samples while in addition to mentioned ones, random coil and aggregates were present in bread samples. Germination of the alfalfa seed induced changes in the protein secondary structure by increasing β -sheets contribution at the expense of α -helix while β -turn share remained unchanged. The β -sheet conformation prevailed in all bread samples except control and bread with 10% ASF where α -helix conformation was dominant. Bread samples containing ASF exhibited increase in β -sheet conformation compared to control, however the inclusion level showed great impact on the main protein structural domain which was β -sheets in 5% bread while that place was occupied by α -helix in the 10% bread formulation. The inclusion of GASF further raised the β -sheet (~50%) as well as random coil share in bread's gluten network regardless of substitution level with simultaneous decrease in α -helix when compared to control bread. The addition of ASF and GASF promoted substantial changes in structural conformation of proteins thus modifying the gluten network. The observed increase in β -sheet conformation regardless of added type of alfalfa seed flour could indicate altered bread quality in terms of volume, and hardness.

Keywords: ATR-FTIR, alfalfa, germination, bread, protein secondary structure

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